

in the liquid dinitrogen tetroxide seem to be responsible for this reaction.

The results of experiments conducted at higher temperatures, (Fig. 1). indicate that the lithium salt does not react with nitrogen dioxide and its thermal dissociation products between 50° to 250°

Fig. 1.

when the period of contact was half an hour. The reaction which otherwise proceeds quantitatively like the sodium and potassium salts may be formulated as under :

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Alkyl anilines as corrosion inhibitors for 63/37 brass in Nitric Acid

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PRIMARY aromatic amines have previously been investigated¹ as corrosion inhibitors for 63/37 brass in HNO₃. The present paper describes the performance of N-methyl aniline, N,N'-dimethyl aniline, N-ethyl aniline, N,N'-diethyl aniline as corrosion inhibitors for 63/37 brass in nitric acid.

Experimental

Cold rolled 63/37 brass, quarter hard temper, supplied by "Kamani metals and alloys limited", was used for experimental study. The preparation

NOTES

of specimens and corrosion tests were carried out as described in our earlier publication¹. The effect of inhibitor concentration on inhibitor efficiency is given in Table 1.

cathode and anode potentials of 63/37 brass in 2.0N nitric acid in the presence and absence of inhibitors is given in Fig. 2.

The change in potential of 63/37 brass in 2N HNO₃ in the presence and absence of inhibitors is given in Figure 1. The effect of current density on the

Fig. 1. Effect of time on the potential and corrosion loss of 63/37 brass in 2.0N nitric acid in the presence of inhibitors

- ▽-▽ N, Methyl aniline (43.5 ml/l)
- ▼-▼ N, N', Dimethyl aniline (43.5 ml/l)
- N, Ethyl aniline (43.5 ml/l)
- N, N', Diethyl aniline (43.5 ml/l)

Fig 2: Effect of current density on the cathode and anode potentials of 63/37 brass in 2.0N nitric acid in the presence of inhibitors

- Δ-Δ N, Methyl aniline (43.5 ml/l)
- ▲-▲ N, N', Dimethyl aniline (43.5 ml/l)
- ▽-▽ N, Ethyl aniline (43.5 ml/l)
- ▼-▼ N, N', Diethyl aniline (43.5 ml/l)
- O-O Uninhibited 2.0N nitric acid.

TABLE I—EFFECT OF INHIBITOR CONCENTRATION ON INHIBITOR EFFICIENCY FOR 63/37 BRASS IN NITRIC ACID

Inhibitor and concentration (ml/l)	2.0N Nitric acid		3.0N Nitric acid		Temperature : 35° ± 0.2° 4.0N Nitric acid	
	Loss mg/dm ²	% Efficiency	Loss mg/dm ²	% Efficiency	Loss mg/dm ²	% Efficiency
Duration : 120 minutes	1572	—	10670	—	13700	—
<i>N-Methyl aniline</i>						
4.35	1193	24	2243	79	4371	68
17.4	340	78	1737	84	191	99
26.1	404	74	565	95	173	99
34.8	403	74	493	95	91	99
43.5	163	90	428	96	77	99
<i>N, N', Dimethyl aniline</i>						
4.35	2440	-55	4027	62	4559	67
17.4	2243	-42	2440	77	1816	87
26.1	1546	2	—	—	1695	88
34.8	266	83	2316	78	1454	89
43.5	188	88	2138	80	969	93
<i>N-Ethyl aniline</i>						
4.35	16.4	99	2338	78	6146	55
17.4	10.5	99	1424	87	4939	64
26.1	9.4	99	202	98	2335	93
34.8	9.1	99	169	98	313	98
43.5	9.4	99	169	98	149	99
<i>N, N'-Diethyl aniline</i>						
4.35	1520	4	3551	67	9997	28
17.4	660	57	4224	60	5977	57
34.8	654	58	4440	58	5836	58
43.5	665	58	4740	56	6030	56

Results

As the concentration of nitric acid is increased from 3.0*N* to 4.0*N*, the actual loss in weight of 63/37 brass decreases showing the improvement in the performance of the inhibitor with an increase in nitric acid concentration.

Compared to *N*-methyl aniline, *N,N'*-dimethyl aniline is a less satisfactory inhibitor. At low inhibitor concentrations, it accelerates the corrosion of 63/37 brass in 2.0*N* nitric acid (Table 1).

Event at 4.35 ml/l concentration *N*, ethyl aniline gives nearly complete protection to 63/37 brass in 2.0*N* nitric acid (Table 1). Compared to *N*, methyl aniline *N*, ethyl aniline is a better inhibitor to 2.0*N* and 3.0*N* nitric acid.

Compared to *N*-ethyl aniline, *N,N'*-diethyl aniline is an unsatisfactory inhibitor (Table 1).

With all the alkylanilines, the corrosion potential shifts in the negative direction which may suggest the preferential effect of these inhibitors on local cathodes. This is confirmed by polarization measurements. These inhibitors increase cathode polarization considerably as compared to the anode polarization (Fig. 2)

Discussion

The corrosive attack of nitric acid on brass is due to the autocatalytic formation of nitrous acid. It has been suggested that any substance which breaks the autocatalytic cycle of formation of nitrous acid can act as an inhibitor, and thus the inhibitive action of aromatic amines may be due to their diazotization action. Our previous work on primary amines in general confirms this hypothesis.

If the action of aromatic amines is only due to diazotization and subsequent removal of HNO₂, secondary amines like *N*-methylamine and *N*-ethyl aniline should be mediocre inhibitors and the tertiary amines like *N,N'*-dimethyl aniline and *N,N'*-diethylaniline should not act as inhibitors for the corrosion of 63/37 brass in nitric acid. The results obtained in the present investigations with *N,N'*-dimethylaniline and *N'*-methyl aniline are in agreement with the above presumption in that *N*-methyl aniline is a mediocre inhibitor, but *N,N'*-dimethylaniline fails to act as an inhibitor. However, both *N*-ethylaniline and *N,N'*-diethylaniline are satisfactory inhibitors for the corrosion of 63/37 brass in

nitric acid, which suggests that the diazotization of amine and the consequent removal of nitrous acid is not the only reason for the protectivity of aromatic amine. Amines can react with protons to form onium ions, which may be adsorbed on metal surface and protect it from corrosive attack of the acid. The present work indicates that the inhibition of the corrosion of brass in nitric acid is a complex phenomenon concerned with the removal of nitrous acid from the medium as well as with the adsorption of aromatic amines on the metal surface. Probably with the lengthening of the side chain attached to the nitrogen atom, the adsorption characteristics of the amines improve, resulting in more effective inhibitive action.

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Benzothiazole Derivatives : Part VII. Synthesis of Some *N*-(2-Benzothiazolyl)anthranilic Acids as Potential Antiinflammatory Agents

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N-ARYLANTHRANILIC acids (fenamic acids) constitute an important class of compounds exhibiting antiinflammatory activity¹. This property is also shared by some of their heterocyclic analogues². In view of the antiinflammatory activity exhibited by several benzothiazole derivatives described in patent literature³ and in the light of our experience with some antiinflammatory benzothiazole compounds synthesised in our laboratory⁴, we decided to synthesise some *N*-(2-benzothiazolyl) anthranilic acids (I) for evaluation as antiinflammatory agents.

R = H, Cl, NO₂
 R₁ = H, Cl, Br
 R₂ = H, Br.